

STRENGTHEN IDEOLOGICAL IMMUNITY OF YOUTH IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: Uzbekistan built as new in our country, that we are the main force in the way of achieving the goal glorious resolve enthusiasm young people with attention and care, show them the opportunities to show their talents and full potential in all areas of the policy and necessary conditions for a state to give priority direction. Youth organizations in international relations at the present stage of development of the national and international level is an important socio-political power. This is not only globalization, and democratization in the conditions of integration processes in the world of modern political lens, enhancing the activity of the developing young, but also young people and support for the promotion of their own interests of the political elite, a serious socio-political force is interested in engaging with the comments. In this article, strengthen ideological immunity of youth in the republic of Uzbekistan, both legal problem has been the basis of the analysis.

Keywords: Ideological immunity, with legal norms, political structures of the modern state.

For determining the legal status of the youth in the modern state, because it is exactly one of the priority tasks of the youth socio-political indicators operates as the development of advanced and innovative in many ways defines the state and society. This socio-political power of its main feature that is the subject of the age. The traditional practice of management science and youth policy of the two is a term that has been considered as the main direction. On the one hand, youth policy and social development of the young generation aimed to show the effects of the state,

political parties, public associations and other entities from the activities of social relations. On the other hand, youth policy – this is intended to support the political direction of his youth in relation to the idea of the political life of the age of the subject, activities, institutions, can be said of the personnel system. The power of youth policy social entities can be different. For example, the legal political parties and public organizations of limited opportunities, but into the minds of the young can be affected by the value concept and ideas. The state, on the contrary, the right to rely on the system, but have less potential to impact through values and ideals from the system. The state youth policy of this young person's self-awareness and youth associations, movements and initiatives for the development of legal, economic and organizational conditions and guarantees of the activity is focused on the creation of the state[1].

In the years of independence of young people in the country, patriotism, respect for national traditions and values, in the spirit of nurturing, physically, spiritually mature and to bring up a healthy generation, in order to protect their rights and interests, certain work is being carried out. At the same time, the situation in the area affected and the measures carried out analysis of topical issues which are wide with a layer of age, especially the young to find their place in the life of to create the proper conditions, comprehensive support, professional referral and employment initiatives is indicative of the organization of work at the level required to stimulate.

In addition, the new state of youth policy in the age of Uzbekistan in the context of independent business, which fits into a new era of social and spiritual qualities, in particular, the important role that mean in the context of globalization, national self-theoretical-methodological and practical basis made up by. S. Shokirova doctor of sciences in the same direction, the essence of his politics, prof. Djurayev revealed in the definition of state youth policy: “this policy is physically and psychologically healthy young people, national-ethnic gene pool of storage, reproduction, development, due to its potential to increase and improve the level of the cell, an active member of the society of every age, as the person focuses on a

combination of trains developed to stimulate the process of socio-economic, political-legal, cultural and spiritual direction of the body, creating a set of conditions targeted towards the society and state separate is the way of political parties and movements”[2].

The President of The Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.Mirziyoyev un in his speech at the session “the future of our planet, our children how to be a human being was associated with the wellbeing of identities. Our main task – is to create the conditions necessary to show the potential of their youth”[3] as was pointed out. Worth mentioning, Shavkat Mirziyoev at the legislation also just signed up as the first president of the republic of Uzbekistan related to the issue of young people, September 14 2016 "on state youth policy" the law[4].

Young legal culture, the development of civil society in the development process and increase their activity building a democratic state; of high moral character, an independent-minded, persistent life position, the patriots, who have a broad outlook and deep knowledge of young people to educate them in different ideological formation of immunity against threats; social protection of young people, to create the proper conditions to be a master of the modern professional, thorough work, and provide them with promotion of entrepreneurship; support for talented young people, creative and intellectual abilities, directed to the realization of the potential of systematically established to work; engage with young people to involve regular physical training and sports, promote healthy lifestyles among young people; and avoid that minors between the age of offenders and crimes committed; harmoniously developed generation, the media and the effective use of modern information and communication technologies are the main directions of youth policy. Identify talented young people, bringing them up to the level of the issue of state policy were raised, in view of the example in our country and gave the opportunity to gather a worthwhile experience. It is noteworthy in the same place, looking for work is aimed at talented young people in the implementation of with a number of them operating in our country government organizations, non-

governmental organizations are also active. For example, the state of youth policy on support for one of the main directions of the youth is of particular significance talents and abilities. Worth mentioning, education, science, technical, information technology, culture, arts, sports, a talented and gifted young people in the fields of business go, healthy support their various initiatives in the direction of pressing the objectives of this organization, one of the tasks set. Knowledge of youth to the level of professional qualifications, qualities like moral and spiritual perfection and social development of the whole society shows a significant effect of the level of quality. Improve living conditions of the population, live from today's modern life is an important indicator in the development of statehood agree to achieve.

Worth mentioning that in recent years, some young folks, come to think about to the benefit of the motherland, independence reached a special feeling to be a useful person in the strengthening of the scientific basis to think on because of the personal interests of the way full of light-aspiration to establish a sense of life to show. In the meantime, some spiritual birth among citizens limit, the narrow outlook of ministry, ethics, comply with national, not the word and the gap between the work, the lack of national pride like this “mass culture” should be to eliminate them but there are other undesirable contours. Today, the most developed and democratic principles based on the values of state ideology. Them in peace and development, human rights and freedom, the idea of religious harmony and national priority [5]. Based on this principle the noble ideas of the interests of mankind, the old dream of the bright future of the human serves. Shavkat Mirziyoyev, the first president of Uzbekistan Islam Karimov as noted in the youth forum, “let's irritate the hands to reform how we are in our country, first of all, young people like you, the power of you-your enthusiasm, we are on to resolve your enthusiasm. Well we all you know, before today we've put our own huge achievements. We have access to the mother country, third in the creation of the renaissance foundation. We are family, preschool, school and higher education and scientific-cultural and is considered the most important element of the future renaissance of ourselves. This radical reforms

in the same areas for the same reason. I'm sure, as you did in creating a new foundation for the development of our country join our active and selfless young patriots, have contributed to”.

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